

COPPER BIGUANIDE CHLORIDE AS A REAGENT FOR THE ESTIMATION OF MERCURY

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A method for the estimation of mercury has been developed by precipitating it from solution as copper biguanide mercuri-iodide, which, after drying at 105°, can be weighed as $[\text{Cu}(\text{BigH}^+)_2]\text{HgI}_4$; where BigH = one molecule of biguanide, $\text{C}_2\text{N}_3\text{H}_7$.

Equality of cationic and anionic volumes, favourable to their close packing in the crystal lattice, is generally regarded as a primary factor leading to low solubility of ionic compounds, particularly with ions of multiple charges. Their inequality results in a loose packing with considerable interionic gaps providing easy accommodation for solvent molecules. With solvent molecules of high dipole moment like those of water the crystalline structure in the latter case is easily attacked and the substance passes into solution. The solubility of an ionic compound can, therefore, be reduced by eliminating the inequality of its cationic and anionic volumes by suitable co-ordinative addition to the smaller of the two ions. For a substance to be soluble the lattice energy must be overcome by that of the hydration of ions. This is generally expressed by the equation: $-U_0 + H = L$, where U_0 = the lattice energy, H = the heat of hydration and L = heat of solution.

Now a compound with a small cation and a large anion, the lattice pattern will usually consist of a close packing of anions in the interspaces of which the smaller cations are lodged as in the structure of silicates. Such a lattice structure is rather loose due to anionic contact. Hence the strong hydration energy of the small cations might often be enough to break down the structure and to make the substance more or less soluble. On the other hand, if both the cation and anion are equally large they will give rise to a close-packed structure with cation-anion contact increasing the lattice energy. But the hydration energy of large cations, which alone is effective, will be comparatively small. This will, therefore, lower the solubility of the compound.

From theoretical considerations it was expected that metal biguanide cations being of large volume will form very sparingly soluble salts when combined with large anions of the type HgI_4^- , CdI_2^- , etc. This was, in fact, already observed before (Ray and Ghosh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 15, 347).

With a view to examining whether any of these sparingly soluble salts might be utilised for the estimation of mercury, the present work was undertaken.

From a preliminary examination it was found that copper biguanide mercuri-iodide is very sparingly soluble and can preferably be employed for the estimation of mercury. Reference may be made in this connection to the fact that Spacu and Suciú (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1929, 77, 334) effected the quantitative estimation of mercury as copper ethylene-diamine mercuri-iodide $[\text{Cu}(\text{en})_2](\text{HgI}_4)$.

When copper biguanide chloride (Rây and Bagchi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 16, 617) is added to a dilute solution of mercuric chloride in potassium iodide, rose-coloured prismatic needle-shaped crystals, which are practically insoluble in cold water, separate out. This precipitate, due to its heavy crystalline nature, settles readily and can be filtered quickly through a porcelain gooch or sintered glass crucible. The precipitate is slightly soluble in presence of ammonia or ammonium salts and also in alcohol.

When dried at 105°, the compound has the composition as shown above and contains 20.6% mercury.

EXPERIMENTAL

Copper Biguanide Mercuri-iodide $[\text{Cu}(\text{BigH}^+)_2](\text{HgI}_4)$, H_2O .

Preparation.—This was prepared by adding a solution of copper biguanide chloride (Rây and Bagchi, *loc. cit.*) to a dilute solution of mercuric chloride in potassium iodide. The rose-coloured prismatic crystals of the compound were washed with cold water and dried to a constant weight in air. The product when heated to 105° to a constant weight becomes anhydrous. 1.5461G. of the air dried substance lost 0.0281g. in weight at 105°. Percentage of water lost = 1.82. $[\text{Cu}(\text{BigH}^+)_2](\text{HgI}_4)$, H_2O requires 1.84% water.

The dehydrated product on analysis gave Cu, 6.61, 6.58; Hg, 20.81, 20.61.

$[\text{Cu}(\text{BigH}^+)_2](\text{HgI}_4)$ requires Cu, 6.53; Hg, 20.6 per cent.

Preparation of the Reagent.—For the preparation of the reagent see Rây and Bagchi (*loc. cit.*). A solution of the reagent may also be prepared from copper biguanide sulphate directly by double decomposition with barium chloride. A 1% solution of copper biguanide chloride was used for the estimation.

Conditions of Precipitation.—The success of this method depends chiefly upon the careful observance of the following conditions:

(a) *Temperature.*—Since $[\text{Cu}(\text{BigH}^+)_2](\text{HgI}_4)$ has got slight solubility, the estimation should be made at temperatures not exceeding 20°. By precipitating at 33° (room temperature in summer) the result obtained was too low. On the other hand, during the reaction copper biguanide chloride forms copper biguanide iodide which is also difficultly soluble. Since there is always an excess of KI in the solution, too low a temperature may cause the separation of $[\text{Cu}(\text{BigH}^+)_2]\text{I}_2$, giving a high result. The optimum temperature was found to lie between 15° and 20°.

(b) *Time.*—It was found that the longer the precipitate was allowed to stand, the better the result obtained. The results were rather low if the precipitate was filtered before the lapse of 4 to 5 hours since its formation.

(c) *Volume.*—The total volume of the mixture must be kept between 100 and 200 c.c. according to the amount of mercury present, to ensure complete precipitation. Too small a volume of the mixture, on the other hand, increases the risk of precipitation of $[\text{Cu}(\text{BigH}^+)_2]\text{I}_2$.

(d) The *concentration* and *amount* of KI must be restricted to the irreducible minimum, just to keep the mercury in solution as HgI_4^{2-} . A 1% solution of KI was found to be most suitable.

(e) A dilute solution of the reagent is to be employed to guard against the precipitation of copper biguanide iodide and also in fairly large excess to ensure the complete precipitation of mercury.

(f) *Other conditions.*—The solution must not contain any other anions except those of halogens, as the complex copper biguanide salts of practically all other anions are sparingly soluble. Ammonia and ammonium salts should also be absent, as they have some dissolving action on the precipitate. The precipitation should be made in neutral solution. In the presence of other anions, the latter must be previously removed by precipitating the mercury as HgO.

Method of procedure.—A 1% solution of KI was added to the neutral mercury solution till the yellow precipitate of HgI₂ first formed just redissolved. 10 C.c. more of potassium iodide solution were then added in excess to prevent the separation of any HgI₂ on dilution to 100-150 c.c. hereafter. A 1% solution of the reagent was then added, drop by drop,

TABLE I

Mercury present.	KI added (1% soln.).	Reagent added in 1% soln.	Total vol.	Temp.	Period of of stand- ing.	Wt. of [Cu(BigH ⁺) ₂] (HgI ₂).	Mercury found.	Error.
0.06813 g.	80 c.c.	50 c.c.	150 c.c.	20°	1 hr.	0.3827 g.	0.07884 g.	Copper biguanide iodide simultaneously precipitated.
0.05676	20	13	200	33.5 (room-temp.)	1 hr.	0.1051	0.02165	Incomplete precipitation
0.06243	10	17	150	20	1 hr.	0.2052	0.04229	Do.
0.05676	20	20	200	20	2 hrs.	0.2617	0.05391	Too low
0.05676	10	30	200	18	2 hrs.	0.2708	0.05580	Low
0.06301	20	18	200	33 (room-temp.)	Overnight	0.2894	0.05962	Too low
0.05961	20	35	125	"	"	0.2841	0.05853	Low
0.06131	10	33	200	15	2 hrs.	0.2925	0.06026	Low
0.05846	10	30.9	200	15-20	3 hrs.	0.2827	0.05824	-0.00022
0.06017	10	31.8	200	15-20	3 hrs.	0.2902	0.05978	-0.00039
0.06244	10	33	200	"	"	0.3013	0.06207	-0.00037
0.06187	10	32.7	200	"	4 hrs.	0.2991	0.06162	-0.00025
0.06357	10	33.5	150	"	"	0.3095	0.06377	+0.00020
0.06528	10	34.5	150	"	"	0.3157	0.06504	-0.00024
0.09082	10	48	150	"	5 hrs.	0.4397	0.09059	-0.00023
0.07947	10	42	140	"	"	0.3850	0.07932	-0.00015
0.09661	10	49	200	"	Overnight	0.4718	0.09718	+0.00057
0.06813	10	36	130	"	5 hrs.	0.3303	0.06805	-0.00008
0.02687	10	15	100	"	Overnight	0.1295	0.02668	+0.00001
0.1022	10	54	150	"	"	0.4971	0.1024	+0.00020

with constant stirring till complete precipitation occurred. It takes some time for the precipitate to appear. An excess of about 20 c.c. of the reagent should be employed.

The precipitate which settles in the form of heavy granular rosy crystals at the bottom of the beaker was allowed to remain at 15-20° for 5 hours or overnight and then filtered through a sintered glass crucible. The precipitate was washed by decantation with a saturated solution of $[\text{Cu}(\text{BigH}^+)_2](\text{HgI}_4)$. When the last drop of the saturated solution was sucked off, 3 c.c. of ice-cold water were used for washing the precipitate and the sides of the crucible. It was then dried at 105° to a constant weight.

The results of a number of experiments carried out under different conditions are summarised in the above table, from which the optimum conditions for determination, as detailed above, will be apparent. The process offers a very rapid and convenient method of estimating mercury apart from the time allowed for standing. A solution of chemically pure HgCl_2 (Scherring-Kahlbaum, *pro analysi* quality) was employed for the estimations. The strength of the solution was also determined by estimating mercury as HgS . In some cases the solid salt (HgCl_2) was directly weighed and used for the estimations.

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